

A superhydrophilic AFM tip as a nanosensor of hydrophobicity: a rationale for a new analytical method

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Accessing surface hydrophobicity (SH) via the water contact angle value (θ_w) at a local (nm) scale, or in a region (nm resolution), is of obvious interest in virtually any field of the natural sciences and related engineering.

To achieve that, the method proposed in this short article exploits the presence of a nanoscale water capillary formed between an AFM tip and any surface in ambient conditions, the characteristics of which depend on the value of θ_w of both the tip apex zone ($\theta_{w\text{-tip-apex}}$) and the surface under study ($\theta_{w\text{-surface}}$), as well as on the tip radius, according to the simplest possible theoretical model. This water capillary is the responsible of the pull-off force ($F_{\text{pull-off}}$) measured by the AFM. The tip radius can be precisely measured by SEM/TEM. The key of this method is that in it, the value of $\theta_{w\text{-tip-apex}}$, a quantity not directly available, is a well-defined fixed quantity. This may be achieved by using a recently released tip material (titanium nitride) instead of the common silicon nitride. Luckily for our purpose, this material bears a perfectly clean, superhydrophilic TiO_2 surface ($\theta_w = 0^\circ$) after a simple modification (surface oxidation and UV-light illumination). The time this effect lasts is well above that taken by the AFM in getting $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ over a region. This way, for each $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ measured, a value of $\theta_{w\text{-surface}}$ can be derived.

In summary, a lucky synergy between a newly introduced tip material and the easiness of fixing its θ_w by rendering it superhydrophilic, makes it possible to obtain a map of SH ($\theta_{w\text{-surface}}$) from a raw $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ map. In other words, it potentially turns the AFM into a fast, local, high-resolution, and quantitative sensor of θ_w or SH.

Keywords: AFM tip; adhesion force; water contact angle; surface hydrophobicity; TiO_2 ; sensors

Graphical abstract

Preprint

58 1. Some fundamentals on surface hydrophobicity, AFM tips and the capillary force in gas-
59 eous environments.

60 Surface hydrophobicity (SH) is a fundamental property that plays a fundamental role in nat-
61 ural phenomena like mineral flotation or protein folding and in the production of commercial
62 goods in the automotive or aerospace (e.g., superhydrophobic coatings), in the biomedical
63 (antibacterial paints), or textile (stain-resistant textiles or flame-retardant and waterproof
64 clothing), to name a few. It is key in the microelectronics since prevents metal oxidation or
65 corrosión.¹ Due to this, much attention has been paid in the past to measure SH, usually
66 focusing on the average surface wettability (statistical average). But most materials are in-
67 herently heterogeneous. Efforts are being made to quantify SH and its distribution at local
68 scales, therefore. AFM or its variations are techniques being used to this end, like Chemical
69 Force Microscopy^{2,3,4,5,6} or Colloidal Probe Microscopy⁷. But these methods do not provide
70 a relationship to values of water contact angle (which is a widespread and facile method)
71 and are conducted underwater and not at environmental conditions. In this proposal, the
72 nanoscale heterogeneity of SH is directly mapped using an AFM derived water contact angle
73 method, under ambient conditions, taking advantage of the ubiquitous water capillary that
74 bridges any asperity (as the AFM tip) and another surface. This is done directly in environ-
75 mental conditions, where many phenomena occur, which should aid higher comparability
76 with the much research that uses the water contact angle.

77 Following the calculations by O'Brien and Hermann and the works of Israelachvili and
78 Riedo^{8,9,10}, when a sphere (tip) of radius R_{tip} is in contact with a flat surface, a capillary
79 annulus of condensed water is formed around the contact surface. The resulting capil-
80 lary/adhesion (pull-off) force, the dominant force in ambient conditions, is:

81
$$F_{pull-off} = 2 \pi R_{tip} \gamma_w (\cos \theta_{w-tip-apex} + \cos \theta_{w-surface})$$
 Equation 1

82 In our proposed setup, $F_{pull-off}$ is maximum, since $\cos(\theta_{w-tip-apex}) = 1$, the highest possible
83 value, so

84
$$F_{pull-off} = 2 \pi R_{tip} \gamma_w (1 + \cos \theta_{w-surface})$$
 Equation 2

85

86 That is, making the tip superhydrophilic maximizes the amount of water the meniscus bear.
87 These experimental conditions make the capillary model even more justified (Fig. 1).

88

90

91 **Figure 1.** Schematics of a $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ measurement using a superhydrophilic AFM tip on a het-
 92 erogeneous surface.

93

94 Since this is a new experimental design, we prefer to present here the simplest possible
 95 theoretical model (limitations found in other studies may not apply here, since the tip wetta-
 96 bility is perfectly defined, and not only that, but it may be considered as clean). Depending
 97 on the success of experiments, researchers may want to use others: they shall find it easier
 98 than with conventional tips since this time the tip wettability is well defined and stable over
 99 the experimentation time (due to its self-cleaning property). But first things first: check the
 100 simplest possible model, that if successful will generate greater interest and broader use.

101 The research about surface forces in gaseous environment is vast and controversial. Since
 102 much of the mismatch between theory and experiment may arise from values of magnitudes
 103 not well accessible experimentally (though well defined in theory), and specially from the
 104 subtle but strong influence of airborne contaminants in both AFM and macroscopic contact
 105 angle measurements (almost any surface exposed to air increases its water contact angle,
 106 even when adsorbed organic compounds can be considered at a trace-level), this research
 107 community may benefit from this new experimental setup.

108

110 2. Easy production of a superhydrophilic (not only highly hydrophilic) tip

111 How can this be done? The starting point comes from nano-industry: some firms have re-
112 cently introduced a novel Ti-based material, say titanium nitride (TiN), for coating their AFM
113 tips. Why has this material been introduced? The main reasons are¹¹: 1) They are conduc-
114 tive (in fact, these tips are usually used in electrical AFM-based measurements); 2) TiN
115 coatings are hard and wear-resistant; 3) Resulting tip curvature are in the range of 40-60
116 nm after coating, which is acceptable; 4) The coating remains in the nm range (about 35
117 nm) and is uniform; 5) It is stress-free and does not significantly bend the cantilever; 6) Shelf
118 life about 3 months (the limitation due to humidity). What is the scientific basis of the process
119 of TiN coverage? These old articles accounts for it^{12,13}.

120 As specified above, these tips are not of general use, so let us describe them and their
121 availability in some detail. These three companies are producing and selling TiN-covered
122 tips. AIST-NT Inc. (USA) (<http://nanoprobes.aist-nt.com/>) Claims to have 15 years of experi-
123 ence in the sector, so a stable service can be expected. It has developed TiN-coated contact
124 AFM cantilevers/tips with resonance frequencies in the range of 10-20kHz and cantilever
125 spring constants (k_c) in the range of 0.03-0.1 N/m (k measures how stiff a cantilever is). The
126 total tip curvature is 40-60 nm, and the height and cone angle are 7-10 μm and $\leq 22^\circ$, re-
127 spectively. The thickness of the coating is about 35 nm. The products names are:
128 fpC10TiN, fpC11TiN, fpC01TiN. Applied NanoStructures, Inc. (USA), known as AppNano
129 (<http://www.appnano.com>). This firm develops conventional and specialized AFM probes.
130 The facilities include a clean room with state-of-the-art characterization tools for rapid pro-
131 totyping, adaptability, and versatility in designing and developing new products. From their
132 website's age, this company has at least 15 years of experience. Their TiN covered tips for
133 contact applications- are called TiN-FORT. They a resonance frequency of 61 kHz and a k_c
134 of 1.6 N/m. The radius of curvature is 30 nm. They also have non-contact or intermittent-
135 contact probes with 37 N/m and 300 kHz values. NT-MDT LLC (Russia) ([https://www.ntmdt-](https://www.ntmdt-si.com)
136 [si.com](https://www.ntmdt-si.com)). IT develops research equipment, primarily atomic force microscopes (AFM) and
137 their combinations with ultra-high resolution spectroscopy. It is represented by companies
138 in Russia, Europe, the USA, and China. It has a history of more than 30 years in the sector.
139 It commercializes TiN-cover tips, compatible with the most of commercial AFM devices. Typ-
140 ical curvature radius of uncoated tips is 6 nm (no data on covered ones). Cone angle at the
141 apex: $7^\circ - 10^\circ$.

142 In conclusion, luckily there are at least three reliable companies producing and selling TiN-
143 coated AFM tips. Now the question is: How can we render these tips superhydrophilic?

144 This is not difficult. Simple treatments are available for a medium sized surface science/ma-
145 terials science lab to oxidise the surface of TiN to TiO₂, the best known self-cleaning super-
146 hydrophilic material (only needs UV-light illumination). One simple way is the ozonisation of
147 the original TiN tip. As described in¹⁴, O₃ oxidizes TiN to form a layer of TiO₂ on the surface.
148 The oxidation reaction, thermodynamically favourable, proceeds as follows:

150 This produces a stable and self-passivating TiO₂ layer that impedes further oxidation. An
151 alternative way, called thermal oxidation, is using heat to oxidize TiN since this material
152 oxidizes to titanium dioxide (TiO₂) at relatively low temperatures, as low as 350 °C in air (Fig.
153 2).^{15,16,17}

154
155 **Figure 2.** Schematics of the process of getting TiO₂ over the surface of TiN.

156
157 How can we render a TiO₂-covered tip superhydrophilic? The phenomenon of turning TiO₂
158 superhydrophilic is well known. It was first reported in a *Nature* paper in 1997 by the group
159 of Prof. Akira Fujishima, from University of Tokyo.¹⁸ They discovered that a TiO₂ surface,
160 whose water contact angle may vary considerably (from hydrophilic to hydrophobic) depend-
161 ing on environmental conditions, becomes superhydrophilic ($\theta_w = 0^\circ$) after being exposed to
162 UV radiation during some hours. Nowadays, this is called the superhydrophilic self-cleaning
163 effect, being this the basis of important applications and product developments^{19,20}. The
164 phenomenon is explained by the production of radical species due to the formation of oxy-
165 gen vacancies at the bridging sections of TiO₂, which has two effects: it induces complete
166 wetting of water and the decomposition of organic contaminant adhered. Particles adsorbed
167 are also carried away by a thin water layer formed at the illuminated surface. Hydrophobic
168 recovery occurs when the material is kept in dark during some (typically some days) or

169 exposing it to heat (typically hours or even minutes^{21,22,23}. Luckily for our purposes, TiO₂ is
 170 one of the few materials that becomes superhydrophilic in such a simple way. UV illumina-
 171 tion is therefore the last step in getting our TiO₂-covered tip superhydrophilic and clean (Fig.
 172 3).

173
 174 **Figure 3.** Schematics of how to transform TiO₂ into superhydrophilic.

175
 176 Needless to say, the k_c and R_{tip} might have changed to some degree due to the TiO₂ layer
 177 grown. Therefore, they must be measured before using the tip. This is straightforward, as
 178 they are usual calibration steps in AFM-based experimentation if one does not want to settle
 179 for the data provided by the companies. R_{tip} can be measured directly by SEM/TEM or indi-
 180 rectly by the blind estimation algorithm, available in various AFM software packages, such
 181 as Gwyddion, WSxM and SPIP^{24,25}. k_c can be measured using the thermal noise method,
 182 among others.²⁶ The whole process of getting a superhydrophilic tip from a bare TiN one is
 183 schematized in Fig. 4.

184
 185 **Figure 4.** Schematics of the whole process of getting a superhydrophilic tip from a bare
 186 TiN one.

187
 188 3. Other surface science research that might benefit from this new experimental design.

189 Though I am a experimentalist, I feel that many previous works reporting a mismatch be-
 190 tween the theoretical models available or developed could be repeated with a well-defined
 191 and stable AFM tip like the one proposed in this note: the mismatches might had been

192 absolutely "impossible to check" factors at time they were conducted: relying in the meas-
193 urement of the wettability of a macroscopic surface of the "same material" than the tip may
194 a good decision since the tip status may vary, even erratically, during an experiment, be-
195 having like a "collector" of adsorbed contaminants²⁷ or simply due to differences arising from
196 the different methods used for synthesizing or processing, even having the same bulk com-
197 position. In the case of using superhydrophilic, self-cleaning tips, their properties remain
198 stable for days.

199 If experimental results require to use other refined theoretical models available in the litera-
200 ture, other variables might be required, such as the tip-surface distance (usually denoted as
201 D), relative humidity (RH), or the rms roughness of the substratum (R_q), which are accessible
202 from AFM data or the environmental chamber

203 Eventually, depending on how successful experiments are, a kind of method-specific "hy-
204 drophobicity" (e.g., superhydrophilic AFM tip derived SH) could be developed, that would
205 add to other existing: for example, the "hydrophobicity-index" used in the biological field to
206 get a numerical estimate of how hydrophobic the cell surface of a bacteria or a fungus is²⁸,
207 the SH derived from capillary AFM interactions with chemically modified tips²⁹, from Chem-
208 ical Force Microscopy^{2,3,4,5,6} or Colloidal Probe Microscopy interactions⁷, or that derived from
209 ESEM images of water micro (not nano) droplets.³⁰

210

211 4. A singular configuration: both superhydrophilic tip and substratum

212 This configuration is particularly interesting because it predicts a fixed value of $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ for a
213 chosen tip. $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ takes here its maximum value (both cosines equal 1), say

$$214 \quad F_{\text{pull-off}} = 4 \pi \gamma_{lv} R_{\text{tip}} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

215 Thus, a measured value of $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ can be used to retrieve a measure of R_{tip} :

$$216 \quad R_{\text{tip}} = \frac{F_{\text{pull-off}}}{4 \pi \gamma_{lv}} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

217 In summary, we could measure $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ on a TiO_2 irradiated substratum previous to the ma-
218 terial of interest as a way of obtaining R_{tip} . This is straightforward: extended TiO_2 surfaces
219 are commercially available (check, for example, MSE supplies,

220 <https://www.msesupplies.com>, or Shinkosha, <https://www.shinkosha.com>). Researcher who
221 have not got access to a SEM or TEM apparatus might find this useful.

222 Again, if experimental data do not fit the theoretical models and the cause might be insuffi-
223 cient water adsorbed for capillary condensation to occur (as some authors have claimed in
224 studies made with conventional tips), relative humidity (RH) inside the environmental cham-
225 ber could be raised until fulfilling the theoretical requirements. This configuration maximizes
226 the amount of water available for formation of the capillary, so my impression is that it worth
227 making the experiments, analysing the data with the simplest model first, and using refined
228 models available in the literature available, if necessary.

229

230 5. A singular configuration: a non-superhydrophilic tip and superhydrophilic substratum

231 An accessory unexpected advantage may come from the measurement of $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ when using
232 a conventional tip and a superhydrophilic substratum (Fig. 5). In this case, equation 1 reads:

233
$$F_{\text{pull-off}} = 2 \pi R_{\text{tip}} \gamma_w (\cos \theta_{w\text{-tip-apex}} + 1)$$
 Equation 6

234

235 **Figure 5.** Schematics of a $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ measurement using a superhydrophilic AFM tip on also
236 superhydrophilic superhydrophilic surface.

237

238 Therefore, the only unknown is $\theta_{w\text{-tip-apex}}$. That is, measuring $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ on a superhydrophilic
239 substratum could be a facile method for measuring/calibrating the wettability of the tip apex.
240 This value could further be used in ulterior studies using another substrate of interest. This
241 would make possible another physical quantity (wettability) of the tip apex, which is the real
242 sensing part, to be accessible experimentally.

243 This is a non-trivial advantage: due to the its nm size, potentially irregular shape or contam-
244 ination, methods to probe its physico-chemical status urge. Whereas it is "easy" to check its
245 physical (shape and general status) by SEM or TEM, which do have nm resolution^{31,32} or
246 using advanced reconstruction algorithms applied to AFM images taken with it, the precise
247 chemical status under the working ambient conditions might be impossible to access, since
248 only TOF-SIMS has the required resolution (nm)²⁷, but as SEM/TEM requires high vacuum
249 and is its capacity of revealing the of molecular nature of the substances present is limited
250 due to the aggressive nature of the ionic bombardment of the surface. Surface wettability
251 $\theta_{w\text{-tip-apex}}$ is an intermediate physico-chemical parameter, but its measurement to such a ul-
252 tras-small region is also challenging. Measuring $F_{\text{pull-off}}$ on a superhydrophilic substratum could
253 provide a solution. If successful, we could well characterize the wettability of an arbitrary tip
254 without relying on the macroscopic water contact angle acquired over a substratum of the
255 "same material" whose surface status might not be "sufficiently equivalent" to reality in the
256 context of magnitudes so exquisitely dependent on the "true surface" as contact angles and
257 surface forces are.

258 Finally, I would suggest another way of testing this obtained value. It would be worth imaging
259 microscopic water droplets nucleated on the tip in an ESEM apparatus, trying to locate the
260 droplets as close to the apex as possible. I only know about microscopic and not nm scale
261 water droplets imaged by ESEM (see my review³⁰ for details), but potentially useful and
262 complementary information may arise in dedicated works.

263

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267 performing applied research, for the much I learned there on the topic of this note.

268

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271

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